

YUFERING Project
YUFE TRANSFORMING R&I THROUGH EUROPE-WIDE
KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

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February 2022

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ERA	European Research Area
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
OS	Open Science
PGR	PostGraduate Research
R&I	Research and Innovation
UANTWERPEN	Universiteit Antwerpen
UBREMEN	Universitaet Bremen
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
UCY	University of Cyprus
UEF	ITA-Suomen Yliopisto
UESSEX	University Of Essex
UM	Universiteit Maastricht
UMK	Uniwersytet Mikolaja Kopernika w Toruniu
UNIRI	Sveuciliste u Rijeci
UNITOV	Università Degli Studi Di Roma Tor Vergata
WP	Work Package
YUFE	Young Universities for the Future of Europe
YUFERING	YUFE Transforming Research and Innovation through Europe-wide Knowledge Transfer

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YUFE Open Science calendar 2022

1. Introduction

As part of the European Research Area vision, the European Commission is aiming to see the necessary transformations in R&I that will include the promotion of citizen science and societal engagement, the mainstreaming of Open Science practices, the fostering of brain and knowledge circulation, strengthening of academia-business collaboration and embodiment in a global Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. The YUFE (Young Universities for the Future of Europe) alliance embraces “YUFE Transforming Research and Innovation through Europe-wide Knowledge Transfer” (YUFERING) this challenge by effectively contributing to pilot these needed transformations to improve and harmonise the conditions for R&I in Europe. Focusing on key elements of the ERA and in full alignment with the relevant SwafS call for proposals, YUFERING proposes ground-breaking transformation actions that will bring the partners one step closer to creating and realising a shared robust R&I vision.

More specifically, WP5 aims to create a YUFE Open Science Strategy and look for a post-COVID-19 approach that states Open Science as “the new normal” in YUFE Universities. In this regard, one of the main objectives is the ‘Engagement/Education/Training: Co-creation of a YUFE Open Education Training Suite on Open Science’. In this scheme, Task 5.4. aims to co-create a training and training and engaging scheme for YUFE researchers about Open Science and, one of the subtasks, is the elaboration of an Open Science Calendar that aims to increase awareness on the open science practices among the researchers (and some intended staff --OS Units, Libraries, Research Support--) from the YUFERING Universities. This deliverable presents this output, from its conceptualization until launch by each one of the partners. The calendar created was a co-joint effort with all the partners and was further customized by each institution, having adopted different dissemination strategies that are detailed in this report.

2. Calendar rationale

In the past few years, a growing number of social scientists have supported a paradigmatic shift in research practices. The OS movement advocates for greater transparency in research and publication processes and the transition from ‘publishing as fast as possible’ to ‘sharing knowledge as early as possible’. In this regard, researchers have a crucial influence on the adoption of OS practices, becoming role models for the change. However, their transition has been very slow so far.

One of the measures discussed to accelerate this transition is the incentives and rewards. Gamification, which is the ‘use of game design elements in non-game contexts’ (Deterding et al., 2011) has proven to be a valuable tool for engaging and motivating desired behaviors. Different studies attested these resources could be a motivation method that works with both conscious and unconscious for incentivizing their practices (Mazarakis & Bräuer, 2020). An example of use and their positive

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response in the scientific community is the badges or progress indicators through social networks/ platforms (e.g. ImpactStory and ResearchGate) (Hammarfelt, Rijcke & Rushforth, 2016) or open science badges that promote data sharing in the health and medical domain (Rowhani-Farid, Allen & Barnett, 2017). These artifacts (e.g. badges) allow promoting best practices, without recipient being conscious. However, those incentives can also be problematic as they exclude or may inadvertently discourage some OS aspects (Fox et al., 2021) (e.g. there is no badge for promoting justice by employing inclusive sampling).

The current year 2022 is a promising year for OS with the unanimous support of UNESCO recommendations (UNESCO, 2021) and with the great commitment of the research stakeholders to change the Research evaluation system (as an example, see this [ongoing coalition initiative](#) from the European Commission). In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic has served as a catalyst in the adoption of OS principles. In this environment, engaging researchers in this path is crucial, as they have the opportunity to have a paradigm shift towards a new way of doing and communicating research. Having milestones that supports this movement in this particular year will allow having faster transition and expand to a larger audience.

In this vein, UC3M and the rest of YUFERING partners have worked on a Calendar design strategy dedicated to the implementation and promotion of Open Science, which is framed into one of the project objectives linked to engagement, education and training (Co-creation of a YUFE Open Education Training Suite on Open Science). Calendar has proven to be a valuable artifact for generating awareness (see Neustaedter, Brush & Greenberg, 2009); however, this has not been applied in the OS at the institutional level (e.g. with the exception of the [Yerun Advent Calendar](#)).

Figure 1 summarises the timeline followed for the realisation of the calendar. During November '21 it was agreed with all partners to define the wide variety of topics (that covers all dimensions of the OS umbrella) and later it was agreed on the co-creation of the monthly messages (November - December 21). During this latter period, the design of the calendar (image selection, text, size) was undertaken. In January '22, the partners started the customization of the calendar (e.g. own language, indicating their own repository) to have a more realistic impact on their researchers. Finally, the calendar was promoted in Mid-January and February (the ways of promotion are specified in the section 4.1.).

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Figure 1. OS calendar timeline

3. Content of the calendar

The design of the content was a co-joint effort between all the members of the task through specific meetings and a shared Google Document. Researchers were agreed to be the target group (as they have a crucial role).

In this vein, the messages were decided to be an overview of all the elements of OS (see Figure 2 and Table 1), having a brief engaging statement as a main message with a related action (very simple for researchers to do) as a sub-message. It was decided to have a SMART criteria (Specific; Measurable; Achievable; Relevant and Time-bound) on the elaboration of each one of the messages. Each one of the institutions adapted some of the actions to their own reality (national or institutional), e.g. their own repository or open science unit website. Additionally, each month has a QR code linking to a specific action (e.g. a survey), video, podcast or any other informative reference (Figure 3). For the calendar design, a selection of open images were selected and properly indicated in the calendar (with information on their license and/or attribution).

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Figure 2, Elements of the Open Science mushroom (@evamen <https://doi.org/10.3989/arbor.2021.799002>)

Table 1. Topics covered by each month

Month	Topic
January	Opening message of the year
February	OS, RRI
March	Open Education
April	Persistent identifiers
May	Research assessment
June	Mentorship
July	Reproducibility and integrity of the research (FAIR data)
August	OS in grant writing
September	Open Peer review
October	Open Access
November	Citizen Science
December	Final reflection

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Image adapted from goodphoto.com (CCO)

If science is not open... it is not going to help us

Open Science and Open Knowledge accelerate research and advance to face social challenges (COVID pandemic, SDGs).

The European Commission and many other political and scientific institutions, as well as research funding agencies, promote the urgent implementation of Open Science.

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN	JAN
					1	2	
3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
10	11	12	13	14	15	16	
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	
24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
31							

QR code:

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YUFE researchers are committed to good practices in Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and are going to be particularly engaged this year with Open Science

Start this journey with a reflection every month to become an Open Scientist.

4-5: Paris Open Science European Conference (OSEC).

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
	1	2	3	4	5	6
7	8	9	10	11	12	13
14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27
28						

FEB

PUT YOUR LOGO HERE

Open education is a way to democratise research and education, adding a positive value to the knowledge created at Universities

7-11 March: Open Education Week. Join this annual celebration as an opportunity to learn about the latest achievements in Open Education worldwide.

Image adapted from the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), p. 11 (CC BY 3.0 IGO)

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
	1	2	3	4	5	6
7	8	9	10	11	12	13
14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27
28	29	30	31			

MAR

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Persistent identifiers are the enablers for building trust and support openness in the digital era

Create/Update your ORCID profile orcid.org and remember that the name of your institution is **R** "Add here the Official name of your institution in ROR" (add your ROR ID for your Institution).

Image adapted from Jørgen Stamp CC BY 2.5 Denmark licence digitalbevaring.dk

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
				1	2	3
4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	12	13	14	15	16	17
18	19	20	21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28	29	30	

APR

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Open Science practices are increasingly included and rewarded in the research assessment

Become a Full Open Science (FOS) researcher: your university supports you.

Image adapted (CC0 Public Domain)

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
						1
2	3	4	5	6	7	8
9	10	11	12	13	14	15
16	17	18	19	20	21	22
23	24	25	26	27	28	29
30	31					

MAY

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Open Science is a must for all researchers. It is preferable to learn these skills in early research stages

Have you done any training in Open Science this year? Become a SOS (Supervisor in Open Science) for your PhD students.

[Universidad Carlos III de Madrid](#) (CC BY-NC-SA 2.0)

	MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
			1	2	3	4	5
	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
	27	28	29	30			

JUN

PUT YOUR LOGO HERE

Findable

Accessible

The reproducibility and integrity of the research are essential principles of any scientific study

Interoperable

Reusable

Sharing and storing research data and making them FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) allows new discoveries, new collaborations and the verification of results and the reproducibility of studies. Share your data whenever possible!

Image adapted from [Yang H. Ku](#) / C&EN / Shutterstock

	MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
					1	2	3
	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
	25	26	27	28	29	30	31

JUL

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Open science is a shift that entails the move from ‘publishing as fast as possible’ to ‘sharing knowledge as early as possible’

Switch your mind!

Start thinking about Open Science practices in your workflow when writing your next grant proposal. Think about opening your publications, data, software, protocols, and methodologies in new eResearch collaborative spaces.

Image adapted (CC0 Public Domain)

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30	31				

AUG

PUT YOUR LOGO HERE

Openness is a clear invitation to quality, rigor and transparency

Open peer review implies greater responsibility and is based on trust and respect and promotes good Open Science practices, such as collaboration and recognition.

Find out how open peer review works in ORE (open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu), EC open access publishing platform.

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
			1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10	11
12	13	14	15	16	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25
26	27	28	29	30		

SEP

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Open access to publications (OA) remains a core element of Open Science

Join the Open Access week. Always upload your publications to the institutional repository ([put the URL of your institutional repository](#)) and retain your rights as long as you publish in scientific publishers with a subscription model. Ask, reflect and open your publications as soon as possible. See: v2.sherpa.ac.uk

Hilda Bastian (CC-BY-NC-ND 2.0)

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
					1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30
31						

OCT

Today more than ever we must do science with and for society

Citizen science is both an objective and a facilitator of Open Science and a fundamental component in the new [European Research Area \(ERA\)](#).

Try including societal groups (citizens, organizations) in your research and discover their potential.

Image by Vlad Tchompalov (CC0) from Unsplash

MON	TUE	WED	THU	FRI	SAT	SUN
	1	2	3	4	5	6
7	8	9	10	11	12	13
14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	22	23	24	25	26	27
28	29	30				

NOV

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Figure 4. Monthly OS calendar screenshots of the English version

This content was adapted by each YUFERING institution, by translating to their own language (e.g. Italian), adding an institutional photo cover or including events of their interest (see examples in Figure 5).

a)

b)

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Figure 5. Screenshots of UNITOV cover (a), UNIRI (d) and UMK (e); Content of January translated to Italian by UNITOV (b) and country-specific content in March by UEF (e.g. workshop on the Policy on Open Educational Practices).

4. Dissemination of the calendar

Table 2 summarizes the particular strategies taken at YUFE partner/university level to better reach and impact researchers with this informative/formative Calendar on Open Science (which is also aligned with the WP6 Communication).

Table 2. Strategies for calendar dissemination

Institution	Particular dissemination strategy adopted by each partner
UANTWERPEN	- OS Calendar was promoted in the University Newsletter - A poster was designed with the calendar
UCY	- OS Calendar was disseminated through social media (Twitter).
UM	- Dissemination strategy is still under development.

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Institution	Particular dissemination strategy adopted by each partner
UBREMEN	- Dissemination strategy is still under development.
UEF	- Calendar was disseminated with the collaboration of UEF communication staff via Yammer (an online collaboration tool) – via groups ‘Current news’ and ‘openUEF’ (group specified on Open Science).
UESSEX	- Calendar was shared through their monthly REO Newsletter (targeting professional services and researchers). - Calendar was shared in the newsletter of the PGR (Postgraduate Research) team.
UNITOV	- Institutional mailing lists were used to disseminate the calendar to the researchers. This also was coordinated with other colleagues working on the YUFE project. - UNITOV institutional newsletter was used (targeted at both researchers and students). - The calendar was shared with the community and research group in Business Administration. - UNITOV spinoff and master contact list and social pages were also used for spreading the word.
UNIRI	- Calendar was published on the UNIRI website. - Another channel of dissemination was through direct email to university colleagues. - UNIRI University library shared the OS calendar on social media platforms, and also uploaded it on the youtube channel.
UMK	- Calendar was placed in several sections on the main web of the University Library. - Promotion Department of UMK and Faculty Libraries also was in charge of their dissemination (e.g. to successively promote, e.g. every month on FB of our library and UMK.)
UC3M	- University Monthly Newsletter included OS calendar. - Video-presentation was included in the UniOS unit (see OS Website). - Calendar was also promoted in the digital screens on the University Campuses. - A DIY-OS Calendar was launched (see details in 4.2. section). - Library Webpage - Collective email from the Vicerrectorship for Research Policies - Calendar was also promoted in the Digital Cafeteria.

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4.1. Examples of dissemination

4.1.1. Newsletter

The majority of the universities used the institutional newsletter as a dissemination channel (as an example, see Figure 6, 7), targeting researchers but also other staff (e.g. students, administrative staff) that could be potentially interested in knowing these practices. This was also relevant, not only in terms of dissemination for the calendar, but also to reinforce the identity of the YUFERING project itself (aligned with the WP6 Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication).

Figure 6. Calendar in the UC3M weekly newsletter (2nd week February edition).

[View in browser](#)

In this newsletter, the Department of Research Affairs & Innovation provides you with all the latest news regarding the university's research and valorisation related activities.

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If Science is not open...it is not going to help us
 Open Science and Open Knowledge accelerate research and advance to face social challenges (the pandemic, the SDGs). The European Commission and many other political and scientific institutions, as well as research funding agencies, promote the urgent implementation of Open Science.

[Review the new UNESCO Open Science Recommendation](#)

Figure 7. Calendar in the Antwerp February newsletter

4.1.2. University website/Library

Some universities decided to promote the calendar through their official website (see UNIRI example in Figure 8) or through the libraries (see UMK example in Figure 9).

Figure 8. Screenshot of the official UNIRI website.

Figure 9. UMK Library website (see the following link)

4.1.3. Social media

Social media (e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn) was another channel used. Here are some examples from YUFERING members (Figure 10).

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Figure 10. Screenshots of some tweets by WP5 leader Eva Méndez; UniOS (Open Science Unit at Uc3m); UMK Library; Members of the project (Elena Christodoulou, UCY coordinator member and Saša Zelenika, UNIRI) (in order of appearance)

All this promotion activity resulted in many reactions on twitter from the academics and even was integrated in some relevant OS events (e.g. [Yerun Open Science Awards 2021](#)) (Figure 11).

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Figure 11. Screenshots of some tweets by researchers and other actors relevant in the field

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4.1.4. Other official channels.

Some partners decided to use additional channels for promoting the calendar. That is the example of UNIRI, who decided to create a Youtube video (Figure 12) with this resource or in the digital Cafeteria at UC3M (which is displayed in all campus screens) (Figure 13).

Figure 12. Screenshot of the UNIRI video on the calendar

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Figure 13. Uc3m digital cafeteria

4.1.5. Informal impact: Internal impact

At UC3M, an additional dissemination strategy was decided by printing the calendars for the researchers. The rationale behind this strategy is the fact that having a physical calendar (placed at work) motivates the researchers unconsciously to take a look at it (and promotes their interaction as an element of their daily life). In addition, it is easy for them to check the QRs (as they do not have to do it on the screens). This initiative resulted in a positive response from the researchers, who shared their gratitude and also some pictures on their calendars on their desks (see Figure 14 with some examples).

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Figure 14. Personal pictures from UC3M researchers

4.2. DIY Calendar campaign

Additionally, members of the UC3M decided to go beyond the limits of the YUFERING project. In order to make this product available for all universities in the world, the research group designed a DIY calendar (with a PowerPoint file and a guideline of use) that anyone could use to set up their own calendar. All this material was uploaded to a [Zenodo repository](#) (which was also included in the [Yufering Community](#)) and a QR was generated to share this resource. Additionally, Eva Méndez (WP5 leader) published an [unboxing video](#) (Figure 15).

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Figure 15. Screenshot of Eva's video unboxing and presenting the calendar and QR to Zenodo resource

In addition, the video was also disseminated in LinkedIn and subtitles were embedded (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Screenshot of Eva unboxing and presenting the calendar

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4.3. Preliminary impact of the calendar

Although the calendar is in its early stage, the different universities have succeeded in disseminating the calendar (as attested by partners' opinions and the wide variety of channels used). The preliminary impact of the calendar is shown in this section.

4.3.1. Zenodo

The DIY calendar was submitted in Zenodo on February 4, having 1,027 views and 733 downloads at the time of writing this deliverable.

4.3.2. Twitter

The video promoting the calendar (at the time of writing, the video had 1,610 visualizations and two original tweets¹ had 22 retweets; and 59 likes). After Eva's campaign on Twitter, this resource has had a relevant impact (885 views and 565 downloads in almost two weeks).

By using Altmetric.com, it was found this resource was mentioned in 75 tweets from 43 users, including OS accounts (e.g. @OpenSciTalk with 3,189 followers; @_open_science_ with 12 mil followers; and @openscience with 71,6 followers) and alliances (University of Bremen Research Alliance (@UBRA_HB) and Leibniz Research Alliance Open Science (@Ifvopenscience). From this source it is also relevant that the tweets are with an upper bound of 159,109 followers. In terms of demographic and geographic information it was disseminated mainly by European users (e.g. Spain, Italy, France), Australia and America and by members of the public (30 users, 70%), scientists (10, 23%) and science communicators (3, 7%) (see Figure 17).

Figure 17. Altmetric doughnut and demographic map

¹ One [tweet](#) for the video and [other](#) for the promoting the Zenodo link

4.3.3. LinkedIn

The unboxing video in LinkedIn had 2,317 visualizations and 191 reactions at the time of writing this deliverable. More details on the impact reached by users of this social media source are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Top-five statistics of users by institution, user's profile and regions

By institution	Nº of views	By user's profile	Nº of views	By regions	Nº of views
Universidad Carlos III	43	University Professor	120	Madrid	312
European Commission	25	Research Fellow	78	Brussels	66
University of Essex	10	Librarian	67	Netherlands	53
Mercadona Tech	9	Project Manager	57	Barcelona	50
Indra	8	Business strategist	56	London	36

4.3.4. International examples of use

During the promotion of the calendar, it was suggested by the WP leaders that all the calendars customized are shared on Twitter with the hashtag #YUFEOSCalendar at @OpenUC3M or by email. To date, some colleagues around the world have shared the calendar on Twitter (see Figure 18, 19).

Figure 18. Animation created and shared through twitter (with the hashtag #VivaElConocimiento) by Lourdes Feria, International Consulting and collaboration with Universidad de Colima (México)

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In addition, other universities and researchers used and customized the material (see Dr. Nader Ale Ebrahim, a freelancer consultant and an adjunct lecturer at Alzahra University, Figure 19).

Figure 19. Post in LinkedIn (left) and screenshot (right) of the cover (Full version available in the following link)

5. Conclusions

Within the YUFERING network, Task 5.4. aims to co-create a training and training and engaging scheme for YUFE researchers about Open Science. In this regard, a calendar output has been created. This report shows how this resource has been constructed, from the design to the construction (that could be easily reproducible in other contexts/further years or currently used by any institution interested in the world).

Being 2022 a promising year for OS, the YUFERING alliance journey has successfully developed a product aligned to this commitment as is reflected in this report. Although it is early to draw conclusions (it will take more time to know exactly the real impact of this artifact) but in a short amount of time has increased the awareness of OA between the researchers and also attract additional interest (e.g. for general audience in Twitter) to this resource and more particularly, to OS.

This resource is mainly created within the YUFERING project to serve the open research community. Their features (adaptability, reproducibility and openly available) made it a potential resource to promote OS practices within researchers from different institutions through gamification. In future deliverables the potential impact achieved by this resource will be analysed.

6. References

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